

Scientific Report – CRSK-2_190843: Fast and Flexible Product Flow Between Processing Stations Through Throwing and Catching

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Introduction

Conveyor belts are the usual means of transporting goods between production stations. However, they require space and contribute to an almost fixed production layout. The aim of this research project is to investigate the possibilities of transportation by throwing and catching, possibly resulting in higher speeds, lower energy consumption and increased flexibility. The long-term goal of the project is the research and development of an industrial concept for a system which can throw, catch, and transmit several products per second. The short-term goal, related to this project, is to realize and investigate a test setup comprised of a thrower, a tracking system, and a catcher with reduced requirements regarding the product throughput.

Scientific Results

Mechanical Design

The experimental set-up consists of two identical, angle-adjustable linear axes, which were developed in-house according to the requirements. Each axis consists of an upright linear rail and a driven sled. The drive is provided by a gearless servo motor via a timing belt and pulley.

The system has been optimised in terms of maximum acceleration and achievable top speed. For this purpose, the mass of the load, consisting of the mass of the sled, the part, and the timing belt $m_{load} = m_{sled} + m_{part} + m_{timingbelt}$, as well as the mass inertia of the motor and pulley $J_{tot} = J_{mot} + 2 \cdot J_{pulley}$ are considered. The inertia of the pulley is approximated by an ideal circular cylinder with radius r_{pulley} , length l_{pulley} , and material density ρ_{pulley} : $J_{pulley} = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \pi \cdot r_{pulley}^4 \cdot l_{pulley} \cdot \rho_{pulley}$. The resulting motor torque is given by $M_{mot} = (m_{load} \cdot r_{pulley}^2 + J_{tot}) \cdot \frac{a_{load}}{r_{pulley}}$. The equation is rearranged according to the acceleration of the load a_{load} :

$$a_{load} = \frac{M_{mot} \cdot r_{pulley}}{m_{load} \cdot r_{pulley}^2 + J_{mot} + \pi \cdot r_{pulley}^4 \cdot l_{pulley} \cdot \rho_{pulley}}$$

To find the optimum, the derivation in respect to r is taken with subsequent zeroing of the numerator, which results in the ideal radius r_{ideal} as a function of the load mass m_{load} , the material density of the pulley ρ_{pulley} , the length of the pulley l_{pulley} , and the motor inertia J_{mot} :

$$r_{ideal} = \sqrt{\frac{-m_{load} + \sqrt{m_{load}^2 + 12 \cdot \pi \cdot \rho_{pulley} \cdot l_{pulley} \cdot J_{mot}}}{6 \cdot \pi \cdot \rho_{pulley} \cdot l_{pulley}}}$$

On this basis, an analysis of more than 100 motor-pulley-timing belt combinations from different manufacturers was carried out, considering the minimum speed and acceleration to be achieved and the design requirements, such as the minimum bending radius of the timing belt or the minimum number of teeth on the pulley.

The sled runs with ball-bearing V-guide rollers on V-guide linear rails, which are screwed onto a profile. The rollers are connected to the middle part of the sled via a swing with integrated springs for each roller. The mounting concept with spacers allows the preload of the rollers to be adjusted. This prevents the rollers from lifting off the guide rails and compensates for manufacturing inaccuracies. For the transmission of the drive force, the timing belt is clamped to the sled. It also holds the interchangeable material storage cone and initialisation stops (cf. Figure 1).

Figure 1: CAD Model of sled on linear rail

Algorithmic and Control

Trajectory Calculation

To determine the velocity required to throw an object over a given distance, the trajectory is calculated considering the air resistance. During the flight, an acceleration $\underline{a}(t)$ acts on the thrown object due to air resistance and gravity that is given by

$$\underline{a}(t) = \begin{bmatrix} a_x(t) \\ a_z(t) \end{bmatrix} = \frac{\underline{F}_w(t) + \underline{F}_g}{m} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{F_{w,x}}{m} \\ \frac{F_g + F_{w,z}}{m} \end{bmatrix} = - \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ g \end{bmatrix} - \frac{c_w \cdot A \cdot \rho \cdot \sqrt{v_x^2(t) + v_z^2(t)}}{2 \cdot m} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} v_x(t) \\ v_z(t) \end{bmatrix}$$

, with the drag coefficient c_w , the thrown object's surface area orthogonal to the trajectory A , the air density ρ , the thrown object's velocity in the x direction $v_x(t)$, and in the z direction $v_z(t)$, the thrown object's mass m , and the gravity g . This results in the differential equation for the position \underline{s} :

$$\begin{bmatrix} \ddot{s}_x(t) \\ \ddot{s}_z(t) \end{bmatrix} + \frac{c_w \cdot A \cdot \rho \cdot \sqrt{\dot{s}_x^2(t) + \dot{s}_z^2(t)}}{2 \cdot m} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \dot{s}_x(t) \\ \dot{s}_z(t) \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ g \end{bmatrix} = 0$$

To determine the required initial velocity \underline{v}_0 from the desired target position, the differential equation must be integrated and solved for the initial velocity. Since there is no closed-form solution for this differential equation, it is necessary to integrate it numerically and calculate the initial velocity iteratively. The initial velocity \underline{v}_0 of the closed-form solution of the differential equation without air resistance is used as the starting value. After the initial velocity \underline{v}_0 has been determined, the Reynolds number Re is calculated to verify the validity of the flow resistance coefficient c_w :

$$Re = \frac{v_{throw} \cdot D \cdot \rho}{\eta}$$

With the throw velocity v_{throw} , the thrown object's diameter D , the air resistance ρ and the air viscosity η .

Influence of Uncertainties on the Calculated Trajectory

To investigate the influence of uncertainties on the calculated trajectory, the trajectory to throw an egg is calculated and afterwards, the parameters are varied by $\pm 20\%$ of their initial value. The resulting influence is shown in Figure 2. An error in the initial velocity v_{throw} has the biggest influence, followed by the gravity g and the throw angle α . The influence of the other parameters can be neglected. However, if a lighter object, such as a ping-pong ball, is thrown instead of an egg, the influence of the other parameters increases significantly. To allow for some degree of uncertainty, the catching area has been increased. This ensures that the catcher catches the throwing object, even if not all parameters are always correct.

Figure 2: Influence of uncertainty for different parameters

Path Planning and Synchronisation

Several given parameters need to be considered for the path planning. First, the motor dictates the maximum acceleration and velocity. On the other hand, depending on the thrown object, the acceleration or deceleration must be limited to avoid damaging the object while it is on the sled. Lastly, the length of the linear axis defines a physical limit. Synchronisation between the thrower and catcher is done in software by calculating the arrival time and point in space based on the calculated trajectory.

A throwing sequence consists of the following steps: 1) Quickly approach the loading position and load the object. 2) Carefully accelerating the object to the required throwing speed. 3) Releasing the object by rapidly decelerating the thrower once it has reached the required throwing speed and halting the carriage before the end of the linear axis. 4) Rapidly moving back to the starting position.

A catch sequence consists of the following steps: 1) Quickly moving to the start position. 2) Rapidly accelerating the sled to the required catching velocity. The catching velocity has to be reached at the previously calculated catching point and needs to be lower than the actual velocity of the object. 3) Maintaining the catching velocity over a certain distance so that the object can land in the catcher. 4) Carefully decelerating the object and halting at the unload position.

Implementation

The implementation was done in EEROS, a real-time robotics framework developed at the OST. EEROS consists of three basic parts: the safety system, the control system and the sequencer which communicate with each other. The communication between EEROS and the servo drives was done over EtherCAT. An overview of the system is shown in the Figure 3.

Figure 3: System overview

Image Processing and Object Tracking

In order to track the flying objects, a GO-2400 camera was positioned perpendicularly to the shooting trajectory. The objective was able to track the whole path, from the thrower to the catcher. The camera delivers images with a rate of 160 frames per second, which allows to get several points along the trajectory. Camera data are processed by Nvidia Jetson Xavier AGX, using software based on OpenCV methods and functionalities. The SDK for the camera provides a sample program to stream camera images. This program was then completed with tracking functionalities.

A reference image is saved before the throwing process begins. The difference between the reference image and the actual frame is computed and those differences are filtered by a threshold. Moving objects are in this way identified. Moreover, the contour of moving objects is identified, and the middle point is saved in pixels units (cf. Figure 4). This will be then saved into a text files with all coordinates of moving objects detected.

Those data are filtered, determining a window where data are expected to be. The trajectories are finally elaborated in MATLAB and compared with theoretical values. In order to get a reference for measurements, ArUco markers are placed on the thrower and catcher robots.

Figure 4: Contour around detected egg in the middle of the flight

Results

The results of the comparison between the calculated and the measured trajectory are depicted in the Figure 5. On the left vertical axis are the actual values and on the right vertical axis the deviation. The calculated and measured trajectory are almost identical, with deviations in the area of 0.05 m in the x direction and 0.02 m in the z direction. The calculated and measured velocities show greater deviations in the area of $\pm 0.2\frac{\text{m}}{\text{s}}$.

To correct the initially calculated trajectory and find the true values, the parameters can be finetuned manually. However, the measurement shown in Figure 5 are with the previously assumed, uncorrected values.

Figure 5: Calculated vs measured trajectory and velocity

Conclusion and Relevance

During the project, a thrower, a tracking system, and a catching system was developed and it was shown that throwing and catching objects can be a feasible alternative to a conventional conveyor belt or transportation vehicle. Due to the possibility of calculating the trajectory with high precision, sensors are not required on the catcher side. A rather simple object tracking with a camera is sufficient to correct possible errors in the calculation and guarantee a soft catching of the thrown object. With the current setup, the throwing rate is primarily limited by the operator, which has to place the object on the thrower and remove it afterwards from the catcher. To increase the throwing rate, a feeding and a discharging unit is required, which should be investigated in a subsequent project.

Deviations from Research Plan

Project Schedule Changes

The initially planned project duration had to be extended twice due to the SARS-COV-2-pandemic. The main reasons were the additional workload to prepare for distance learning, the inaccessibility of laboratory equipment and the prototype during the home office period, and delayed deliveries of suppliers due to the lockdown.

Personnel Changes

Due to intern personnel changes and to evenly distribute the mentioned additional workload arising from the distance learning, personnel adjustments had to be made. Initially Romano Hauser was employed with the software development and the evaluation and integration of the sensors. Jonas Frei and Claudia Visentin replaced him during the project. Both of them have a comparable educational background and skills.

Changes of Deliverables

Due to time constraints, the recalculation of the trajectory was not performed once new data became available. Instead the previously described post-throw image processing was implemented. Also due to time constraints, the grasping and depositing of goods was replaced by a simple catcher. As the experiments showed, no additional sensors were needed on the thrower or catcher besides the camera, so they were omitted. The Magnus effect was neglected because the object has no spin or other significant rotation during flight. Lastly, the throwing distance of 4 to 5 meters defined at the beginning of the project was not quite reached. For some unknown reason, the motors do not reach their specified torque, which limits the maximum acceleration and thus the maximum throwing speed.

Description of Contributions Made by Project Staff

Name	Affiliation	Gender	Position	Main tasks
Jonas Frei	OST	Male	WiMa ¹	Project management Software development (algorithmic and control) Testing
Ueli Scherrer	OST	Male	WiMa ¹	Mechanical design Commissioning
Claudia Visentin	OST	Female	WiMa ¹	Software development (image processing and object tracking)
Romano Hauser	OST	Male	WiMa ¹	Actuator evaluation Theoretical flight path calculation
Moritz Lammerich	OST	Male	WiMa ¹	Installing EEROS and EtherCAT on Beckhoff PC
Roland Steinauer	OST	Male	WiMa ¹	Ancillary work
Einar Nielsen	OST	Male	Prof ²	Coaching and support on mechanical, control and software topics
Urs Graf	OST	Male	Prof ³	Coaching and support on software topics

Table 1: contributions made by project staff

Research Output

Documentation, source code, scripts, videos and results are available on Zenodo.

¹ Wissenschaftlicher Mitarbeiter (Research Assistant)

² Professor for automation

³ Professor for informatics